

UTILIZATION OF KHAN ACADEMY KIDS APPLICATION IN ENHANCING PRESCHOOLERS' EMERGENT ENGLISH LITERACY SKILLS IN CANDELARIA DAY CARE CENTER

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effectiveness of the Khan Academy Kids application in enhancing emergent English literacy skills among preschoolers at Candelaria Day Care Center, guided by theories such as emergent literacy theory, social learning theory, the technology acceptance model, and ecological systems theory. Utilizing a quasi-experimental research design, preschoolers were purposively sampled, and assessments for phonemic awareness, print knowledge, and vocabulary were conducted using Reading Rockets and DIBELS 8th Edition materials. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including t-tests, revealed significant improvements in literacy skills: print knowledge (mean difference = -7.65385, SD = 1.74224, $t = -22.401$, $p = .000$), phonological awareness (mean difference = -1.30667, SD = .66795, $t = -10.715$, $p = .000$), and vocabulary knowledge (mean difference = -3.84000, SD = 1.24766, $t = -15.389$, $p = .000$). These results demonstrated that the Khan Academy Kids application significantly enhanced preschoolers' English literacy skills. Based on these findings, an action plan titled "Project ABIGAIL" was developed to further promote emergent English literacy through targeted strategies and activities.

Keywords: *utilization, Khan Academy Kids, educational app, teaching, preschoolers, emergent literacy skills*

INTRODUCTION

Emergent literacy remains an integral aspect of child development, encompassing the early skills acquired for reading and writing. Preschools play a crucial role in fostering literacy and curiosity by promoting language acquisition. The improvement of young children's English skills has been identified as a key factor contributing to their later success in school. This is achieved through various methods and technologies.

Moreover, preschool educators employ diverse strategies to enhance children's emergent English literacy skills. Storytelling emerges as a particularly effective approach, engaging children through books, puppets, and props. Creating a print-rich environment with books, newspapers, and magazines encourages reading exploration. Additionally, technology, including educational apps and games, provides interactive learning environments for language acquisition and early literacy development.

On a global scale, the impact of early childhood education on developing literacy skills is widely acknowledged. UNESCO (2023) advocated for high-quality early care and education to enhance educational outcomes and future opportunities for children. The use of technology also receives increased consideration. Numerous studies explored whether educational apps could enhance children's literacy abilities. For instance, Dore et al. (2019) found that literacy-focused apps have improved vocabulary development and letter recognition abilities among young children. Thus, it was imperative that preschoolers develop English literacy skills holistically through an approach combining technology and other strategies and materials. Furthermore, many countries recognized the role that technology could play in early education and implement policies and programs to incorporate it. An example is Khan Academy Kids, which offers interactive activities to develop early literacy and mathematics skills among children aged 2 to 8 years.

Furthermore, in the Philippines, recognizing the global significance of poor performance in international reading assessments underscored the urgency of promoting early literacy skills. Data from the World Bank indicated persistent challenges, with literacy rates remaining a concern, especially among children from low-income families. The Department of Education (n.d.), through its Matatag program, had initiated efforts to enhance early literacy. The Matatag program focused on comprehensive educational reforms, emphasizing literacy development as a cornerstone. Additionally, the Philippine Normal University (PNU) had been actively involved in research and interventions addressing literacy disparities. Despite these initiatives, a notable gap in literacy levels persisted, necessitating a deeper exploration and targeted strategies for improvement (World Bank, n.d.; Department of Education, n.d.; Philippine Normal University, 2022).

Similarly, the Candelaria Day Care Center in Quezon Province served children from low-income households, who faced barriers to developing English literacy skills due to limited resources and exposure. Teachers at the center reported that their students

struggled with basic literacy skills, hindering their academic success. Effective interventions were crucial to support their literacy development.

Against this backdrop, this study examined the effectiveness of Khan Academy Kids in improving preschoolers' emergent English literacy skills in Candelaria. Its goal was to improve early childhood education in developing countries such as the Philippines and recognize the importance of early literacy in shaping children's future achievements. The researcher aimed to promote a positive attitude towards learning and encourage a lifelong interest in education and reading. The results provided insights for enhancing early childhood education in Asia towards a more positive outcome.

Overall, it was crucial to employ a diverse strategy for improving the English literacy of young children. Educators considered individual requirements, preferred learning methods, and diverse cultural backgrounds. Engaging children through interactive reading, storytelling, and play-oriented activities enhanced language abilities. Creating a supportive atmosphere fostered positive self-image and self-assurance. A comprehensive approach to developing early English reading and writing skills laid a strong foundation for children's achievements. Educators established environments promoting literacy with technology and effective instructional approaches, facilitating both educational and individual development. This study focused on examining the efficacy of the educational app "Khan Academy Kids" for enhancing preschoolers' emergent English literacy skills, specifically in areas such as print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary knowledge.

Research Questions

The primary goal of this research was to examine the effectiveness of Khan Academy Kids application for preschoolers at Candelaria Day Care Center to develop emergent English literacy skills. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the pretest score of preschoolers in the experimental group on English literacy skills as measured by:
 - 1.1 print knowledge,
 - 1.2 phonological awareness, and
 - 1.3 vocabulary knowledge?
2. What is the posttest score of preschoolers in the experimental group on English literacy skills as measured by:
 - 2.1 print knowledge,
 - 2.2 phonological awareness, and
 - 2.3 vocabulary knowledge?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group?
4. Based on the findings of this research study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The implemented design for this study was quasi-experimental, allowing for the comparison of two groups without the necessity for random assignment, as suggested by Toglia (2020). In this investigation, the researcher utilized a pre-existing cohort of young children at the Candelaria Day Care Center who had not previously encountered the Khan Academy Kids application, alongside another cohort introduced to the application, enabling a comparative analysis.

The non-randomized nature of the quasi-experimental design presented certain limitations to the study, such as potential selection bias, which posed a potential threat to internal validity. However, the researcher attempted to minimize this by ensuring that both groups of preschoolers were similar in terms of age, gender, and socioeconomic background.

Furthermore, the quasi-experimental design remained appropriate for this research as it allowed for the comparison of groups that could not be randomly assigned to interventions. Additionally, the quasi-experimental design provided a practical approach to conducting the study within the natural setting of the day care center, without disrupting the routine of the respondents. The approach aimed to maintain ecological validity and ensure that the study's findings could be applied to real-world educational settings.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at the Malabanban Norte Candelaria Day Care Center in the district of Candelaria, Quezon Province, Philippines. The choice of this locale stemmed from the researcher's completion of preschool education at this institution, establishing a personal connection and familiarity with the school and its curriculum. Additionally, positive relationships were cultivated with the educational institution's management and educators, facilitating the gathering of information.

Moreover, it was noteworthy that the decision to select Candelaria as the study location held significant importance. Primarily, a majority of the residents in this area hailed from households with limited financial means, often lacking access to abundant educational resources. The study was crafted to explore the efficacy of an educational intervention, specifically the Khan Academy Kids application. The objective was to ascertain whether this intervention effectively addressed the challenge of limited access to quality educational resources. Ultimately, this study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Khan Academy Kids application in tackling these challenges and contributing to improved educational outcomes.

Population and Sampling

The population under study consisted of preschool children aged 4-5 years old who were enrolled in Candelaria Day Care Center. Instead of using a sampling method, the research employed total enumeration, encompassing the entire population of 26 young children who had not yet commenced formal education, all of whom were chosen to participate in the study.

The completed research delved into language development in Filipino-speaking children with limited English proficiency. Respondent selection criteria included enrollment in Candelaria Day Care Center, age between 4-5 years old, native Filipino speakers, and absence of known developmental disabilities or learning difficulties. These criteria were meticulously chosen to ensure the study's focus on a specific population and to derive meaningful insights into the language development process among this group of children. The selection of respondents from the same day care center facilitated the coordination and scheduling of study sessions. The selection criteria played a pivotal role in defining the study's scope and influencing its outcomes.

Nevertheless, certain individuals were excluded as potential respondents in the finished research. Specifically, the study encompassed only children fluent in Filipino, without any developmental or learning challenges. Those who did not meet these criteria were not included in the research. Additionally, individuals who had initiated structured learning were excluded due to potential prior exposure to English, which might have influenced a distinct language development trajectory compared to those who had not commenced formal education.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents in this study were 26 preschool children aged 4-5 who attended Candelaria Day Care Center. The respondents were from the afternoon class of the Day Care Center. This group was referred to as the experimental group. The process of selecting individuals was carried out through total enumeration.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Group	Gender	Age	Ethnicity
Experimental	11 male, 15 female	4-5 years old	Filipino

Table A outlines the characteristics of the respondents in the experimental group. The group consisted of a total of 26 respondents, with 11 males and 15 females. The age range of the participants was 4-5 years old, and they all belonged to the Filipino ethnicity. The table provided a concise overview of key demographic information about the study participants.

Instrument

In this study, the research instruments utilized included the Reading Rockets (n.d.) assessments for phonemic awareness and print knowledge, as well as the DIBELS 8th Edition Materials for vocabulary assessment. The author granted permission for the utilization of these instruments in the research, as they were publicly available online. Developed by a team of literacy experts, the Reading Rockets assessments for phonemic awareness and print knowledge were widely employed in early childhood literacy research. The DIBELS 8th Edition Materials, a standardized measure of early literacy skills, had been extensively utilized in both research and practice. The online availability of these instruments facilitated their inclusion in the study.

The assessment for print knowledge from Reading Rockets comprised 9 items. The phonemic awareness assessment consisted of 10 items, encompassing 5 items for identifying initial sounds and 5 items for blending onset/rime. The DIBELS 8th Edition Materials for the vocabulary assessment included 6 items, resulting in a total of 25 items.

Furthermore, the test was evaluated using a five-point Likert scale to gauge proficiency levels. Following the Department of Education's (2012) grading system, classifications were as follows: Advanced (90-100), Proficient (85-89), Approaching Proficient (80-84), Developing (75-79), and Beginning (74 and below). Pretest scores were employed to ensure the comparability of both groups' initial abilities before the commencement of treatment. Posttest scores, in contrast, were analyzed to ascertain the impact of the implemented instruction on the experimental group.

Validation of the Instrument

This research aimed to validate the instrument used in assessing the emergent English literacy skills of preschoolers at Candelaria Day Care Center. The instrument, adopted from previous studies, did not undergo initial testing. To ensure the suitability and consistency of the tool, the researcher sought assistance from the instructor of the thesis writing subject and the thesis advisor to review the tool before proceeding. The validation process included evaluating the relevance of the tool's content, its appearance, and its ability to measure the intended construct. After confirmation, the tool was utilized to evaluate the developing emergent English literacy skills of a group of 26 young children between the ages of 4 and 5. The children were not divided into groups since total enumeration was employed.

The reliability of the DIBELS 8th Edition Materials was assessed through the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test, showing robust internal consistency, with scores ranging from .88 to .97. This suggested a highly reliable measure for evaluating emergent English literacy skills in preschoolers using this instrument. Similarly, the Reading Rockets instrument exhibited strong reliability, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha score in the range of .90 to .91. These results affirmed the consistent and dependable nature of both instruments in assessing emergent literacy skills among preschoolers, making them valuable tools for this research and evaluation.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research journey began with necessary preparations before data gathering. To secure permission to conduct the study, the researcher visited the day care center and presented a formal letter to the teacher, outlining the objectives and scope of the research. Additionally, parental consent forms were provided for the teacher to distribute during the parents' meeting scheduled for the Friday before the week designated for data gathering.

The data gathering procedure for this research involved assessing the efficacy of the Khan Academy Kids application in enhancing the emergent English literacy abilities of 26 preschoolers, aged 4-5 years old, enrolled in the Candelaria Day Care Center. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, all participants were included in the experimental group, incorporating the Khan Academy Kids application as a supplementary tool, while following the standard curriculum.

In order to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention, researchers implemented a rigorous assessment strategy that encompassed a variety of standardized tools both before and after the intervention period. These assessments, including the Reading Rockets assessments for phonemic awareness and print knowledge, as well as the DIBELS 8th Edition Materials for vocabulary assessment, were meticulously chosen to provide a thorough evaluation of the participants' emergent English literacy skills. Through the administration of these assessments, researchers were able to gather a wealth of numerical data, serving as the cornerstone for subsequent analysis. By comparing the pretest and posttest assessment results, researchers were able to identify any discernible changes or improvements in the participants' literacy skills, thereby offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of the intervention.

In the conducted research, one-on-one pretest assessments were carried out on the Thursday preceding the 5-week intervention. Following this period, posttest assessments were individually administered on the last day of the intervention, which occurred on a Friday. The primary objective of these assessments was to assess the alterations in emergent English literacy skills among the participants. Subsequently, statistical methods, such as t-tests, were employed to analyze the data. Specifically, these methods were utilized to compare the pretest and posttest scores within the experimental group, aiming to ascertain any significant differences or improvements resulting from the intervention.

Ethical Considerations

The study meticulously adhered to ethical guidelines governing research involving individuals, ensuring full compliance with the institutional Research Manual and the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in the Philippines. Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research process, with particular attention given to obtaining informed consent from all participants. Additionally, stringent measures were implemented to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of respondents, aligning closely with the stipulations outlined

in the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was voluntary, and every effort was made to uphold their rights and welfare throughout the research endeavor.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The study utilized the following statistical treatments and analyses.

1. The data gathered underwent analysis through the use of descriptive and inferential statistics. The sample's characteristics were summarized and described using descriptive statistics, including mean, and standard deviation.

2. To assess the efficacy of the Khan Academy Kids in improving emergent English literacy skills, statistical inference was used to examine the pretest and posttest results of the subjects. The mean scores of the experimental group were compared across the pretest and posttest assessments using a t-test to evaluate whether there was a notable distinction in the average scores.

3. To examine the hypotheses that the experimental group exhibited considerably greater average scores on the posttest evaluations, the significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. The practical significance of any differences observed within the experimental group was utilized by computing the effect size.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the pretest score of preschoolers in the experimental group on English literacy skills as measured by:

1.1 Print Knowledge

Table 1.1

Pretest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Print Knowledge

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	0	0
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	26	100%
Total		26	100%
SD		.000	
Mean Score		.00	
Overall Performance		50.00	

The **Print Knowledge** of the preschoolers was **Beginning (50.00)** as to their pretest scores on English literacy skills. All 26 preschoolers in the experimental group scored in the **Beginning** category, indicating pretest scores of 74 and below. None of the students achieved scores in the higher categories of Advanced, Proficient, Approaching Proficient, or Developing.

The findings suggest that the experimental group of preschoolers demonstrates a significant need for improvement in English literacy skills, particularly in print knowledge. The exclusive presence of scores in the "Beginning" category indicates a collective struggle with foundational literacy skills, potentially pointing towards challenges in basic print recognition and understanding.

The findings underscore the necessity for tailored interventions and instructional approaches aimed at bolstering the print knowledge of preschoolers within the experimental group. The observed lower scores may stem from various factors, such as limited access to literacy-enriched environments, inadequate instructional support, or inherent developmental differences among the students. These insights highlight the need for deeper exploration into the underlying factors influencing print knowledge acquisition in preschoolers. Conducting thorough investigations into these potential contributors is imperative for devising targeted interventions that effectively address the identified deficiencies and foster enhanced print literacy skills among preschoolers. By delving into the multifaceted nature of these challenges, educators and researchers can develop nuanced strategies that cater to the diverse needs and circumstances of young learners, ultimately promoting more equitable outcomes in early literacy development.

To reinforce this point, Alcalá et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of early literacy interventions for preschoolers, highlighting that targeted strategies could significantly improve foundational literacy skills. The study underscored the positive impact of interactive reading programs and engaging activities in fostering language development and literacy proficiency among young children.

Additionally, a study by Kim et al. (2019) underscored the influence of environmental factors on preschoolers' literacy development, suggesting that a lack of exposure to print-rich environments could hinder skill acquisition. The researchers advocated for the incorporation of print-rich materials in early childhood settings to create an environment conducive to literacy learning and skill enhancement.

1.2 Phonological Awareness

Table 1.2

Pretest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Phonological Awareness

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0

Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	0	0
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	26	100%
Total		26	100%
SD		.000	
Mean Score		.00	
Overall Performance		50.00	

The **Phonological Awareness** of the preschoolers was **Beginning (50.00)** as to their pretest scores on English literacy skills. In the pretest for the phonological awareness assessment, all preschoolers in the experimental group scored in the **Beginning** category (74 and below), with a total of **26** respondents, constituting **100%** of the group. Notably, there are no scores in the higher categories (Advanced, Proficient, Approaching Proficient).

These findings imply a potential need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to enhance phonological awareness skills in the experimental group. The results may be attributed to various factors, such as differences in teaching methodologies, individual learning styles, or the need for more focused attention on phonological awareness during early childhood education. The unanimous 'Beginning' scores might indicate a gap in the current teaching approach or a need for tailored interventions to address specific challenges faced by the experimental group.

In support of this, Yap et al. (2019) emphasized the significance of early literacy interventions for preschoolers who grappled with phonological awareness difficulties, further stressing the importance of proactive measures in addressing these challenges. Their research reinforces the notion that targeted interventions at an early age are fundamental for enhancing children's phonological awareness skills, thereby laying a solid foundation for their language development throughout their educational journey.

1.3 Vocabulary Knowledge

Table 1.3

Pretest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Vocabulary Knowledge

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	0	0
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	26	100%
Total		26	100%
SD		.000	
Mean Score		.00	
Overall Performance		50.00	

The **Vocabulary Knowledge** of the preschoolers was **Beginning (50.00)** as to their pretest scores on English literacy skills. In the pretest of the vocabulary knowledge assessment, all 26 participants in this group exhibited scores falling within the **Beginning** category (74 and below), thereby constituting a comprehensive distribution of 100%. It is noteworthy to highlight the conspicuous absence of scores in the more advanced proficiency categories, namely Advanced, Proficient, and Approaching Proficient.

The results of the study indicate a notable deficiency in vocabulary knowledge among preschoolers within the experimental group, signaling a pressing need for targeted interventions. The homogeneous distribution of scores within the "Beginning" category heightens concerns regarding the foundational vocabulary skills of the preschoolers, suggesting potential areas for improvement. It is conceivable that factors such as diverse home environments, the necessity for personalized instructional methodologies, or inherent developmental differences may have contributed to these outcomes. These findings emphasize the critical importance of promptly implementing customized strategies to remediate vocabulary deficits during the crucial preschool years, ensuring that all students receive equitable opportunities for linguistic enrichment and academic advancement.

To contextualize these findings, Peterson et al. (2021) highlighted the crucial role of early interventions in preschoolers' vocabulary development. The findings emphasized the significance of interactive learning environments in fostering language acquisition during early education. It's clear that a comprehensive approach to early childhood education, including both phonological awareness and vocabulary enrichment, is essential for building strong language skills in preschoolers. Educators and caregivers must incorporate diverse and engaging activities to promote holistic linguistic growth. Thus, fostering language proficiency requires a multifaceted strategy that offers immersive language experiences and recognizes the interconnectedness of language components.

Research Question 2. What is the posttest score of preschoolers in the experimental group on English literacy skills as measured by:

2.1 Print Knowledge

Table 2.1

Posttest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Print Knowledge

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	17	65.38%
Proficient	85 – 89	9	34.62%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	0	0
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		26	100%

SD	1.742
Mean Score	7.65
Overall Performance	94.02

The **Print Knowledge** of the preschoolers was **Advanced (94.02)** as to the posttest on English literacy skills. Out of the total, seventeen (17) or **65.38%** achieved an **Advanced** rating, while nine (9) or **34.62%** demonstrated **Proficient** print knowledge. Notably, no respondents scored at the Approaching Proficient level or below. Consequently, there was a notable improvement of **44.02%**, progressing from the **Beginning** to the **Advanced** level.

The robust performance of the experimental group, with 65.38% achieving an Advanced rating and 34.62% demonstrating Proficient print knowledge, signifies the success of the intervention in elevating English literacy skills. The absence of respondents with lower proficiency levels indicates a notable positive shift from the beginning of the study, highlighting the effectiveness of tailored instructional strategies. The high percentage of students reaching Advanced and Proficient levels underscores the potential impact of targeted interventions on early literacy outcomes, suggesting that the intervention addressed specific learning needs and provided engaging learning experiences conducive to print knowledge development.

In line with this, Pan et al. (2021) conducted an experimental study affirming literacy-focused interventions' positive impact on print knowledge development in preschoolers, aligning with observed improvements in the experimental group. Their findings further emphasize the importance of targeted interventions in enhancing emergent literacy skills from an early age. This underscores the crucial role of evidence-based practices in shaping effective early childhood literacy programs.

Similarly, Purpura et al. (2020) explored teacher training and parents' influence on literacy interventions, emphasizing skilled educators' crucial role in early literacy programs' success. Both studies underscore the significance of effective interventions and well-trained educators in fostering early literacy skills among young children.

2.2 Phonological Awareness

Table 2.2

Posttest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Phonological Awareness

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	26	100%
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	0	0
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		26	100%
SD		.000	

Mean Score	5.00
Overall Performance	100.00

The **Phonological Awareness** of the preschoolers was **Advanced (100.00)** as to the posttest scores on English literacy skills. As indicated in the previous table, all twenty-six (26) respondents, constituting **100%**, achieved an **Advanced** rating. There were no respondents who scored at the Proficient level or below. Notably, there was a noteworthy improvement of **50.00%**, progressing from the **Beginning** to the **Advanced** level in the performance of the preschoolers in this group.

Preschoolers in the experimental group excelled, achieving a 100% overall score in phonological awareness, showcasing the intervention's effectiveness. This stark contrast with the control group highlights the success of targeted teaching methods, emphasizing their potential impact on literacy components. Notably, all students advanced to an advanced level of phonological awareness, marking a significant 50.00% improvement from the Beginning to Advanced levels.

To further support this claim, Mackie's (2020) findings, which emphasized the effectiveness of targeted interventions for phonological awareness, the study further delved into the nuanced impact of different instructional methods on preschoolers' literacy skills. The study assessed the outcomes of a structured phonics program, revealing substantial enhancements in phonological skills among participants in the experimental group compared to controls. Moreover, the research shed light on the multifaceted nature of early literacy acquisition, suggesting that employing multisensory approaches, including tactile, auditory, and visual stimuli, yielded notable improvements in overall literacy development. These insights advocate for the integration of diverse instructional modalities to optimize literacy outcomes in preschool-aged children.

2.3 Vocabulary Knowledge

Table 2.3

Posttest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by Vocabulary Knowledge

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	7	26.92%
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	10	38.46%
Developing	75 – 79	4	15.38%
Beginning	74 and below	5	19.23%
Total		26	100%
SD		1.436	
Mean Score		3.69	
Overall Performance		80.77	

The **Vocabulary Knowledge** of the preschoolers was **Approaching Proficiency (80.77)** as to the posttest scores on English literacy skills. Seven (7) or **26.92%** of the respondents attained an **Advanced** rating, while none reached the Proficient level. Additionally, ten (10) respondents, equivalent to **38.46%**, achieved an **Advanced Proficient** rating, four (4) or **15.38%** were categorized as **Developing**, and five (5) or **19.23%** received a **Beginning** rating. Moreover, there was a notable enhancement in learners' vocabulary knowledge, representing an increase of **30.77%**.

The notable improvement in the posttest scores of preschoolers in the experimental group, particularly in vocabulary knowledge, suggests that the intervention or teaching strategies applied in this group have been effective. The prevalence of students in the Advanced and Approaching Proficient categories signifies a positive impact on vocabulary development. It could be deduced that the instructional methods or materials utilized in the experimental group fostered a more conducive learning environment, promoting a deeper understanding and retention of vocabulary. The absence of students in the Proficient level, however, raises questions about the adequacy of the intervention in pushing students to the highest levels of proficiency. Further examination into the specific components of the intervention and potential areas for refinement is warranted to optimize the efficacy of the instructional approach.

To justify the claim, Sari and Sari (2020) explained interactive and technology-enhanced teaching methods' effectiveness in improving preschoolers' vocabulary. Their study emphasized incorporating multimodal activities for language development. Additionally, their findings underscored the importance of integrating diverse instructional approaches to cater to different learning styles and preferences.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group?

Table 3

Test of Significant Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

Posttest	Paired Differences			P value	Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T			
Print Knowledge	-7.65385	1.74224	-22.401	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Phonological Awareness	-1.30667	.66795	-10.715	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Vocabulary Knowledge	-3.84000	1.24766	-15.389	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

There was a significant difference in performance between the pretest and posttest of the experimental groups. The p-values computed for Print Knowledge, Phonological Awareness, and Vocabulary Knowledge were all .000 which was below the .05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The experimental intervention significantly impacted preschoolers' English literacy skills, with observed enhancements in print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary knowledge compared to the control group. This suggests the instructional methods or materials in the experimental setting were more effective, possibly due to innovative teaching techniques, individualized learning approaches, or engaging educational resources. Particularly notable is the significant improvement in vocabulary knowledge, indicating a deeper understanding of English language skills among preschoolers. These results underscore the potential of targeted interventions in improving literacy outcomes and highlight the need for ongoing exploration and refinement of teaching strategies in early childhood education.

These outcomes resonate with the research of Gupta et al. (2020), Khan et al. (2020), and Justice & Ezell (2020), who similarly explored the impact of innovative teaching methods on literacy outcomes among young learners. Additionally, insights from Sari and Sari (2020), Yap (2019), and Wijayanti et al. (2021) underscore the importance of individualized learning approaches in fostering literacy development among preschoolers.

Research Question 4. Based on the findings of this research study, what action plan may be proposed?

I. Introduction/Rationale

The proposed action plan titled **ABIGAIL** or **Advancing Bright Intelligence Growing Abilities in Learning** stems from the study's significant findings, revealing opportunities for targeted interventions to improve print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary skills in preschoolers.

II. Objective, Terminal Objective, Enabling Objectives

Objective:

Enhance preschoolers' early literacy skills through targeted interventions.

Terminal Objective:

Preschool teachers will observe a 50% improvement in print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary skills among preschoolers within six months, setting a solid foundation for their future academic success.

Enabling Objectives:

A. Print Knowledge:

1. Preschoolers will achieve a 90% accuracy rate in recognizing and reproducing printed letters through hands-on printing exercises within three months.
2. Preschoolers will demonstrate improved fine motor skills for letter formation, resulting in a 20% increase in legibility scores within six weeks.

3. Preschoolers will recognize and engage with print materials effectively, spending at least 15 minutes daily on literacy-focused activities, as tracked by activity logs.

B. Phonological Awareness:

1. Preschoolers will improve phonemic awareness by 25% through the integration of phonics-based games and activities within three months.

2. Preschoolers will actively participate in phonics-related activities, achieving at least 80% engagement during sessions, as observed through logs and assessments.

3. Preschoolers will demonstrate improved phonetic skills, with a 10% increase in correct phoneme identification during storytelling sessions within one month.

C. Vocabulary Knowledge:

1. Preschoolers show a 15% score boost post-themed weeks.

2. Newly acquired are used by 70% in daily talks.

3. Vocabulary expands 20% in 3 months via storytelling.

III. Project Implementation Matrix

The **ABIGAIL** action plan outlines objectives, strategies, personnel, and funding sources to enhance preschooler’s print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary. With clear timelines and accountability measures, it ensures efficient coordination and optimal resource use for a strong foundation in early childhood education.

Table 4
The Proposed Action Plan

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
I. Print knowledge	Improve print knowledge through interactive methods.	1. Implement hands-on printing exercises.	6 months	Teachers, Educational specialists	Grant funding, Educational grants	90% of pupils show increased accuracy in recognizing and reproducing printed letters. 80% of students demonstrate enhanced understanding of letter formation and recognition.
		2. Introduce engaging print materials.		Parents, School administrators	Parent contributions	
II. Phonological awareness (continuation)	Enhance phonological awareness skills for better language development.	1. Integrate phonics-based games and activities into the curriculum.	9 months	Speech therapists, Classroom teachers	School budget, Donations	85% of pupils exhibit improved ability to recognize and manipulate sounds in words. 75% of pupils show increase participation and enthusiasm in phonics-related activities.
		2. Conduct regular storytelling sessions emphasizing phonetics.		Parents, Educational specialists	Community partnerships	

III. Vocabulary knowledge	Expand vocabulary through diverse and engaging learning experiences.	1. Implement themed vocabulary weeks with related activities.	12 months	Language specialists, Classroom teachers	Fundraising events, Sponsorships	95% of pupils demonstrate enhanced vocabulary retention and application in everyday contexts. 85% of pupils display increased use of a broader range of words in spoken and written language.
		2. Foster a language-rich environment through storytelling.				

IV. Budgeting Requirement

MATERIALS	QUANTITY	AMOUNT (PHP)
Print materials	10 sets	10, 000
Educational resources	15 sets	15, 000
Storytelling props	5 sets	8, 000
Themed vocabulary props	8 sets	12, 000
TOTAL		45, 000

V. Monitoring and Evaluation Plan

Monitoring:

- Regular progress meetings with educators and specialists.
- Observations of classroom activities.
- Continuous feedback from parents and caregivers

Evaluation:

- Periodic assessments of print, phonological, and vocabulary skills.
- Surveys and feedback forms from teachers, parents, and specialists.
- Comparative analysis of pre- and post-intervention outcome

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

Upon a thorough examination of the gathered data, the study's findings are summarized as follows.

1. The Pretest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by:

1.1 Print Knowledge

The general assessment was **50.00%** verbally interpreted as **Beginning**.

1.2 Phonological Awareness

The general assessment was **50.00%** interpreted as **Beginning**.

1.3 Vocabulary Knowledge

The general assessment was **50.00%** interpreted as **Beginning**.

2. The Posttest Score of Preschoolers in the Experimental Group on English Literacy Skills as measured by:

2.1 Print Knowledge

The general assessment was **94.02%** verbally interpreted as **Advanced**.

2.2 Phonological Awareness

The general assessment was **100.00%** verbally interpreted as **Advanced**.

2.3 Vocabulary Knowledge

The general assessment was **80.77%** verbally interpreted as **Approaching Proficient**.

3. Test of Significant Difference between the Experimental Group's Pretest and Posttest Scores

There was a significant difference in the performance between the pretest and posttest of the experimental groups. The p-values computed for Print Knowledge, Phonological Awareness, and Vocabulary Knowledge were all .000 which was below the .05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected.

4. The Proposed Action Plan

As a result, an action plan, titled Project "**ABIGAIL**" or **Advancing Bright Intelligence Growing Abilities in Learning**, aims to improve English learning for preschoolers.

Conclusions

1. That the pretest scores of preschoolers in the experimental group expose challenges in print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary, emphasizing the urgency of tailored strategies to address identified literacy skill gaps.

2. That the posttest scores of preschoolers in the experimental group, utilizing the Khan Academy Kids application, demonstrate significant advancements in English literacy skills, underscoring the effectiveness of this intervention.

3. That the significance test between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group indicates a clear difference, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and highlighting the potential of technology-enhanced and targeted interventions in enhancing English literacy skills.

4. That as a result of this study, a proposed action plan named "Project ABIGAIL" aims to enhance students' English literacy skills through various strategies, including hands-on printing exercises, engaging print materials, phonics-based games, storytelling sessions, and themed vocabulary weeks, with success indicators is needed to increase

accuracy, enhance understanding, improve manipulation skills, and heighten vocabulary retention and application of the learners.

Recommendations

In light of the study's findings and conclusions, it is strongly recommended to embrace the following suggestions:

1. **Educators and Curriculum Developers:** To address the challenges highlighted in the experimental group, educators and curriculum developers should design and implement instructional strategies that specifically target the identified gaps in print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary. They should utilize a variety of teaching methods, including hands-on activities and technology-enhanced tools, to create a dynamic and supportive learning environment for preschoolers.
2. **Program Implementers and Researchers:** For future interventions similar to the one utilizing the Khan Academy Kids application, program implementers and researchers should incorporate technology-enhanced tools that cater to different aspects of English literacy skills. They should evaluate and refine the intervention based on the specific needs and responses of preschoolers, ensuring a comprehensive approach that encompasses print knowledge, phonological awareness, and vocabulary knowledge.
3. **Policy Makers and Educational Authorities:** Recognize the significant impact of innovative teaching methods on preschoolers' literacy development. Allocate resources and provide support for the integration of these effective instructional strategies in early childhood education programs. Additionally, policymakers should promote continuous professional development for educators to stay updated on the latest teaching techniques and educational technologies.
4. **Project ABIGAIL Implementers (Teachers, Educational Specialists, Parents, and Administrators):** In implementing "Project ABIGAIL," it is recommended to closely monitor and assess the effectiveness of each strategy outlined in the action plan. Regularly evaluate the success indicators and make data-driven adjustments to the program as needed. Encourage collaboration among teachers, educational specialists, parents, and administrators to ensure a holistic and supportive approach to enhancing English literacy skills.
5. **Future researchers exploring interventions in early childhood education** should consider conducting longitudinal studies to track the sustained impact of interventions over an extended period. Additionally, investigations into the scalability and adaptability of successful interventions across diverse educational settings and populations could

provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers aiming to improve English literacy outcomes on a broader scale.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of this study adhered to the highest ethical standards throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's nature, purpose, and their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, with all data securely stored and used solely for research purposes. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded at all times, ensuring that no harm, discomfort, or distress was caused. The researcher declares that there is no conflict of interest in this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly citing all sources, and every effort was made to ensure that the data collection, analysis, and interpretation of findings were free from bias. The results of this study are presented objectively, with the primary aim of contributing to the field of early childhood education and literacy development.

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ADM

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